

How to cite: Tsotsas, I., Papanikolaou, Z., & Goulas, A. (2025). Emerging trends in business sustainability: A bibliometric analysis in innovation practices. *International Conference on Next-Generation Innovations and Sustainability 2025*. Futurity Research Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15098298>

Emerging trends in business sustainability: A bibliometric analysis in innovation practices

Ilias Tsotsas¹, Zacharias Papanikolaou², Apostolos Goulas³

¹*Economist, Service Design, PhD Candidate, International Hellenic University (Serres), Greece*

²*Agricultural Economics, PhD, Post Doctoral Researcher, Democritus University of Thrace, Greece*

³*Economist, Agricultural Economics, PhD, University of Thessaly, Greece*

Accepted: March 11, 2025 | **Published:** March 27, 2025 | **Language:** English

Abstract: Global trends now focus on the environmental issue, sustainable development goals and corporate social responsibility. Businesses will now have to adapt to new data, new and innovative approaches to gain a competitive advantage and improve their sustainability performance. This bibliometric analysis deals with emerging trends and innovative practices in the field of business sustainability and specifically with sustainable food businesses. The paper highlights the trends and innovative practices related to business sustainability in the period from 2019 to 2024. Finally, the records were collected from Scopus database and analyzed using Vosviewer software tool.

Keywords: business sustainability, innovation practices, sustainable food business, bibliometric analysis, sustainability

Introduction

With the growth of e-commerce over the last twenty years, the concept of business model has become increasingly popular. Research in this area has grown rapidly and especially in recent years

with ma research activity varying and covering a wide range of application areas. In line with sustainable development objectives, innovative business models give a competitive advantage to improve the sustainability performance of organizations. According to Nosratabadi et al (2019), the concept of sustainable entrepreneurship describes the logic of how an organization creates, delivers and captures value in economic, social and cultural contexts in a sustainable manner.

The rise of environmental issues such as climate change, the expansion of innovation in our daily lives and the evolution of technology have transformed the market and the behaviour of stakeholders which leads to a reorientation of the model, strategy and missions of companies (Bilan et al, 2020). In this case, company managements are required to transform existing models and trends from a traditional model to a sustainable one (Ye et al, 2020).

In recent years, a lot of research has been conducted on sustainable business and innovation. In particular, the general relationship between the two (Harsono et al,2024),business strategy,business models and sustainable innovation(Aggarwal et al,2024;Bilan et al,2020) green innovation and strategies (Kar & Harichandan,2022;Zhang et al, 2024), social innovation and entrepreneurship (Foroudi et al,2021;Chu et al,2022), sustainable business practices , digitalization and technology (Kwong et al, 2023). The main objective of the above studies is the long-term sustainability of businesses. However, there is no recent research on the emerging trends of sustainable business and analysis of innovative practices, resulting in this gap in the literature.

Research Aim and Research Questions

This research is called upon to fill this gap and answer the lack of clear mapping of emerging trends and innovative practices as the world faces major environmental, economic and social challenges and to survive in the long term, businesses are required to incorporate innovative sustainability practices. Although there are bibliometric studies on sustainable entrepreneurship, they do not capture the latest developments and many of them are limited to older data. The purpose of this paper is to help researchers and businesses understand the field and to highlight innovative practices that businesses can adopt to improve their environmental and social performance. To this end, it is called upon to answer the following research questions:

- *What are the dominant trends in sustainable food business from 2019 to 2024?*
- *What innovative practices have been most associated with business sustainability from 2019 to 2024?*

In this paper, Scopus was chosen as it is a database widely recognized by the academic community and trusted for its selection standards. According to Echchakoui (2019), the integration of Scopus by Elsevier and its wide accessibility by universities worldwide make it an indispensable tool for bibliometric analysis.

Research Results

To conduct the bibliometric analysis and to investigate scientific publications, we used the Scopus database. The keywords we used to search the documents in Scopus were "sustainable business" and "sustainable food business". These keywords were searched in the document titles, abstracts and keywords. This search resulted in 1955 articles. The keywords of these articles resulted in the emerging trends and innovative practices that we are looking for in this paper. Also, some restrictions were placed on the search of the papers in the Scopus database. Initially the search was only done to find scientific articles and conference papers. We chose to analyze conference papers as well since we study the emerging trends that imply new ideas and findings. Conference papers

are usually faster to publish than scientific articles and a trend may emerge that has not yet been published in a scientific journal. Also, emerging trends in a relatively new field such as sustainable business are likely to be presented first at conferences and then published. The bibliometric analysis was performed only on the keywords of documents published in the period from 2019 to 2024 as we are only interested in new trends and practices of sustainable business. The selected documents are all written in English.

Finally, the tool chosen to conduct the bibliometric analysis was Vosviewer 1.6.20 with which the bibliometric map was constructed and visualized. Vosviewer was chosen as the tool for the bibliometric analysis because it is a specialized tool for such analyses and visualizations of bibliometric networks, as it creates easy-to-use maps of collaborations, keywords and bibliographic links.

Emerging trends and innovative practices

In this section we examine the emerging trends in business sustainability according to the results extracted from the vosviewer software (see figure 1). Also, from the analysis of keywords apart from emerging trends, we also examine innovation practices. All the results we got are from the keywords of 1955 articles and are for the period from 2019 to 2024.

As expected, the term "*sustainability*" has the most occurrences as a keyword (297 occurrences) as it is a general term and the keywords with which we searched the articles have a direct link to sustainability. Sustainability as well as "*sustainable development*" (119 occurrences) are considered among the general principles of sustainable development that influence business strategies (Ruggerio, 2021). For this reason, they are also long-term trends for sustainable business and not only for the period under study. The "*circular economy*" (101 occurrences) is considered one of the most contemporary trends in many scientific fields as well as in the field of business sustainability as it is one of the key strategies for the development of sustainable strategic models. The circular economy undoubtedly has significant sustainability potential. However, its limited conceptual grounding and weak link to sustainable development have allowed 'circular economy solutions' to be proposed that have adverse sustainability implications. Then the term "*food waste*" appears 77 times as a keyword. Food waste is part of the overall waste management. Food waste is a critical challenge. Effective waste management and reduction of food waste can benefit the sustainability of businesses as they can enhance business reputation, reduce costs and ensure compliance with environmentally friendly legislation. "*Food security*" (79 occurrences) is according to the results an important factor that can ensure the quality of food production by reducing the risks that may exist and can promote sustainable agricultural practices. These can be achieved through "*supply chain*" stability (Vagsholm et al, 2020), which enhances business sustainability (37 occurrences). Food security and supply chain can reinforce business sustainability as it can enhance consumer confidence, business reputation and competitiveness.

According to the results, the innovative practices that appear as keywords in the articles we studied are mainly four (see table 1). In particular, "*sustainable agriculture*" (28 occurrences) and "*agriculture*" (45 occurrences) which involves practicing agriculture in an environmentally friendly way, protecting biodiversity without the use of chemicals. Food production can also be enhanced by the use of new innovative technologies that improve the efficiency and sustainability of agricultural practices (Jararweh et al, 2023). "*Food industry*" (39 occurrences), innovation in the food industry can increase competitiveness, enhance new product creation and generally improve processes that address the continuous changes in consumer satisfaction. The term "*innovation*" (48 occurrences) is

a general term used in almost all sectors. In the food industry it involves the creation of new products and services using new and innovative technologies that can enhance efficiency, sustainability and quality.

Table 1

Most popular keywords in business sustainability literature the last 5 years

Source: developed by the authors

Keyword	Occurrences
Sustainability	297
Sustainable development	119
Circular economy	101
Food security	79
Food waste	77
Covid-19	51
Innovation	48
agriculture	45
Food	40
Food industry	39
Climate change	39
Supply chain	37
Sustainable Development Goals	36
Sustainable agriculture	28
Business Model	26

Figure 1

The visualizing map of papers on the sustainable business in food industry.

Source: developed by the authors using VOSviewer

Conclusions

This research answers two research questions regarding emerging trends and innovative practices in business sustainability and specifically in sustainable food business. In terms of emerging trends

sustainable business is associated with circular economy, food waste, food security, supply chain which have a strong impact on sustainable business. Also, the terms sustainability & sustainable development also play an important role which influence the strategies of businesses. Regarding innovative practices, it is clear that great emphasis should be placed on sustainable agricultural practices and the integration of innovative technologies that will enhance the production process. Innovation is generally a key factor in any industry and in the business sustainability sector can improve competitiveness and sustainability by helping businesses to adapt to new trends and market demands. The evolution of technology and the constant changes in market requirements make business sustainability a dynamic field that is constantly evolving. Thus, there is a wide range of topics that could be studied in the future. For example, the role of the circular economy in food businesses or the impact of new technologies on sustainable agricultural production could be studied.

References

- Aggarwal, A., Baker, H. K., & Joshi, N. A. (2024). Organizational innovation as business strategy: A review and Bibliometric analysis. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*, 1-27. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13132-024-01830-2>
- Bilan, Y., Pimonenko, T., & Starchenko, L. (2020). Sustainable business models for innovation and success: bibliometric analysis. *E3S Web of Conferences*, 159, 04037. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202015904037>
- Chu, M., Muhamad, H. B., Mustapha, M. B., San, O. T., Zan, F., & Jia, X. (2022). Research Trends in Corporate Social Responsibility and Innovation: A Bibliometric analysis. *Sustainability*, 14(21), 14185. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142114185>
- Foroudi, P., Akarsu, T. N., Marvi, R., & Balakrishnan, J. (2020). Intellectual evolution of social innovation: A bibliometric analysis and avenues for future research trends. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 93, 446-465. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmarman.2020.03.026>
- Harsono, T. W., Hidayat, K., Iqbal, M., & Abdillah, Y. (2024). Creating Sustainable Innovation Performance: A systematic review and Bibliometric analysis. *Sustainability*, 16(12), 4990. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16124990>
- Jararweh, Y., Fatima, S., Jarrah, M., & AlZu'bi, S. (2023). Smart and sustainable agriculture: Fundamentals, enabling technologies, and future directions. *Computers & Electrical Engineering*, 110, 108799. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compeleceng.2023.108799>
- Kar, S. K., & Harichandan, S. (2022). Green marketing innovation and sustainable consumption: A bibliometric analysis. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 361, 132290. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.132290>
- Kwong, R., Kwok, M. L. J., & Wong, H. S. M. (2023). Green FinTech Innovation as a Future Research Direction: A Bibliometric Analysis on Green Finance and FinTech. *Sustainability*, 15(20), 14683. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su152014683>
- Ruggerio, C. A. (2021). Sustainability and sustainable development: A review of principles and definitions. *Science of the Total Environment*, 786, 147481. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.147481>

- Vågsholm, I., Arzoomand, N. S., & Boqvist, S. (2020). Food Security, Safety, and Sustainability—Getting the Trade-Offs right. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 4. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2020.00016>
- Ye, N., Kueh, T., Hou, L., Liu, Y., & Yu, H. (2020). A bibliometric analysis of corporate social responsibility in sustainable development. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 272, 122679. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.122679>
- Zhang, J., Taqi, S. A., Akbar, A., Darwish, J. A., Abbas, S., Alam, S., Gao, Y., Shahbaz, M. Q., & Butt, N. S. (2024). Green Innovation in Business: A comprehensive bibliometric analysis of trends, contributors, and future directions. *Sustainability*, 16(24), 10956. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su162410956>